

6. SaxFDM-Tagung

20-21 November 2025
Dresden, Germany

SCAVENGER HUNT

Instructions:

The first letter of each of the **11 answers** can be combined to a solution phrase.

Hint:

The clues can be found only in or around the Klemperer-Saal.

The clues can be found only in or around the Open Science Lab.

Hand in your solution at the registration desk no later than 04:00 pm on 20. November 2025 to participate in a little tombola!

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(Given name / Surname)

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